

Extra-political Contacts across the B/Orders: Otherness, Culture and Order

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Abstract

The aim of this article is to explore the implications of the Order/Culture nexus in world politics as related to processes of othering and alterity formation. The contemporary international order brings together states, communities, and individuals with different ways of approaching the world. Meanwhile, it is inevitably hard to ignore the often sharply divisive shifts that penetrate the fabric of the global liberal order. This contestation surrounding the concepts of an international liberal order shows to what extent this contestation is not just about power transitions but reflects the conflicting narratives of the global—cultural, nationalist, ethnic, racial, historical, colonial, and religious. While stability in international politics is a defining element of how order-builders seek the constitution of political legitimacy, these contesting narratives present the global order with a legitimation crisis. This requires not only maximising material capabilities but also an aspiration to choreograph and organise cultural diversity into authorised forms of expressions, or diversity regimes. This article is particularly interested in how these diversity regimes are integral to the ways in which postcolonial orders prioritise and organise cultural differences in alignment with the established distribution of political authority. Analytic insights from the Constructivist and Post-colonial theory will help account for the discursive formations and representations of alterity and otherness, which I argue are another manifestation of diversity regimes. These formations rest upon a particular view of contemporary world order: the characteristic distinctiveness that drives interaction among actors, and which, in turn, constitutes different alterities: “ally,” “rival,” “friend,” and “exotic.”

Keywords: culture; order; Alterity-Otherness formation; postcolonial theory; International Relations theory

1. Introduction

The contemporary international order brings together states, communities, and individuals with different ways of approaching the world. Meanwhile, it is inevitably hard to ignore the often sharply fracturing power shifts that penetrate the fabric of the global liberal order: the rise of non-Western great powers, the return of ethno-nationalism and populism spearheaded by far-right leaders, and the resurgence of anti-globalisation sentiments (whether understood as Americanisation, Westernisation, cultural imperialism, or modernisation).¹ These transformations present the international liberal order with a new intense reality: although the contemporary pluralist order is presented as a culturally homogeneous context capable of accommodating all forms of cultural diversity and power transitions, it is also an order in which the organisation of these different articulations of cultural diversity is deeply intertwined with the configuration and legitimisation of political authority. This intense contestation surrounding the concepts of an international liberal order shows just to what extent this contestation is not just about power transitions but reflects the conflicting narratives of the global—cultural, nationalist, ethnic, racial, historical, colonial, and religious. This reality shows the complex nature of cultural diversity by probing a conventional conception of international order anchored in a longer tradition of thinking in mainstream International Relations (IR) scholarship²—one in which order is established, in addition to sovereignty, by cultural homogeneity. This means international orders develop in common, unified cultural contexts. These assumptions about the nature of world order and culture show to what extent the view of cultural diversity as a challenge to the current international order depends on a particular view of culture.³

The governance of cultural diversity is a key imperative in building and sustaining political legitimacy in world politics.⁴ If these global shifts were once

considered purely geopolitical turnabouts, their entanglement with deeper structures of culture and hegemony shows they are not just geopolitical but also cultural in nature. Disciplinary debates in mainstream IR, however, attribute these global changes, and with them the new expressions of cultural difference, to transitions in material capabilities. Often backed by positivist and materialist epistemologies to make sense of these new conjunctions of material power, mainstream IR theory conceives culture as an epiphenomenal event—only loosely constitutive of the international order, and only relates to world politics in ways that are (preferably) empirically causal. It presents the modern polity as a culturally integral, unitary and inclusive order.

This default conception of culture, commonly shared by realists and neo-liberals, is not without problems. The cultural homogeneity thesis suggests that a culturally homogeneous context is a prerequisite condition to sustain order, preserving the “more” important binding role that align the different articulations of cultural diversity to open, “rules-based” institutions such as foreign policy establishment, diplomacy and international law. According to this conception, thus, institutions have but only a “neutralising effect” through which culture is strategically instrumentalised in order to create opportunities for cooperation and coordination. Yet, as Reus-Smit notes, this thesis conceals the very organisational role of these institutions in, not necessarily neutralising cultural differences, but in organising diversity itself into authorised forms of cultural diversity.⁵

Stability in international orders is a defining element of how order-builders seek the constitution of political legitimacy. This requires not only maximising material capabilities and assets but also an aspiration to choreograph and organise cultural diversity into authorised forms of expressions. These defining moments take the form of “diversity regimes”: “systems of norms and practices that simultaneously configure authority and construct diversity. Codified in formal institutions, such as treaties and conventions, and embedded in informal

understandings and social practices”⁶. Post-colonial orders are a relevant context where these cultural entanglements are enmeshed with global flows (political, economic and cultural). This article is particularly interested in the extent to which these diversity regimes are integral to the ways in which postcolonial orders prioritise and organise cultural differences in alignment with the established distribution of political authority.

2. Cultural “Diversity Regimes” and the Systemic Configuration of Political Authority

What is at stake for the future of the modern international order is not whether these new articulations of cultural diversity are threatening the very fabric of the neoliberal order, but how these cultural conjunctions are assimilated into the workings of the international order. Such conjunctions present the neoliberal order with various legitimation challenges and crises to sustain order, with which new “diversity regimes” are mobilised to contain diversity. There are three incentives which drive policy-makers to organise and contain diversity: control, coordination and satisfactions of ecumenical sensibilities.⁷ In such contexts, international orders are best conceived as systemic configurations of political authority. Order requires a sense of legitimacy which rests on an aspiration for hegemony and the conversion of material power into political might, as well as an aspiration to domesticate diversity into authorised and hierarchical forms of difference.

There are many ways in which we can approach these diversity regimes. What is important to note here is that institutions and social structures provide the fundamental framework to channel these regimes and their subsequent norms and narratives. These diversity regimes do three things: “First, they legitimize certain units of political authority—states, empires, cities, etc.—and define the scope of legitimate political action. Second, they define recognized categories of cultural difference (religion but not civilization or nation, for example), and order these

normatively (Catholics, Lutherans, or Calvinists, but not Anabaptists, Muslims, or Jews). And, third, they relate legitimate units of political authority to authorized categories of cultural difference (sovereign state and religion, empire and civilization, etc.).”⁸

Insights from new histories of the Ottoman Empire’s code of *Millet* and the Lifan Yuan system of Qing China, for instance, suggest that international orders have always emerged within heterogeneous, loosely integrated cultural contexts.⁹ The Westphalia Peace Treaty of 1648 which brought to an end the Eighty Years’ War is often taken as a case to illustrate how shared norms of a cooperative culture are capable to accommodate diversity and perpetual peace and take over the Hobbesian logic of “war of all against all”. Yet it also shows how European leaders were keen to resort to a rather institutional solution, through which diversity regimes permeate different units of authority to create cultural hierarchies and patterns of inclusion and exclusion.

3. Into the Definitional Fray: the Constructivist View of Culture

Exploring the nexus between culture and order is rudimentary in today’s mainstream IR and outside the field. Exploratory insights of this kind helps understand not only the global cultural flows that are already taking place among states and foreign peoples (whether those that grow organically between nations or those that are established by states’ official practices and institutions), but also how the very idea of culture itself is politically configured to exert power and authority. One conceptual challenge that arises here, however, is the elusive nature and semantically loaded meanings of the term culture itself. Raymond Williams famously noted that culture is “one of the two or three most complicated words in the English language.”¹⁰ The difficulty of defining culture is due to the fact that it is so inclusive that it is hard to know what to exclude.

Despite these definitional constellations, IR scholars always make assumptions about culture and its workings within international politics. The literature concerned with the study of culture within the scope of mainstream IR theory offers different explanations and conceptualisations of the role of culture in the construction of world politics and international orders—clash of civilisation (Samuel Huntington, 1996),¹¹ culture of national security (Peter Katzenstein 1996),¹² Social Constructivism (Alexander Wendt, 1999),¹³ Soft Power (Joseph Nye, 2004),¹⁴ and Cultural Diplomacy¹⁵. It is at this point where we come to grips with the central home turf issue that flies in the face of mainstream IR scholarship: how policy-makers and scholars make sense of new cultural conjunctions and power transitions depends on a particular view of culture.

IR scholarship loomed large during the aftermath of the two world wars of the last century. As bodies kept piling up, scholars became very concerned about the causes of war and the possible conditions for peace. This ‘problem-solving’ commitment of IR theory was soon to be expanded into questions such as the legitimacy of foreign policies, military intervention, causes of conflict and conditions for cooperation. As the field kept growing, so did its theoretical scope. Diversity in theory and its root metaphors caused splits within the field and presented academia with competing frameworks of viewing and approaching world polity. This ‘problem-solving’ commitment is often paired with positivist and materialist ontologies to make sense of these new conjunctions of material power, driving mainstream IR debates to conceive narrowly of culture as an epiphenomenal event—only loosely constitutive of the international order, and only relates to world politics in ways that are (preferably) empirically causal.¹⁶

While this default conception of culture sticks to a more positivist¹⁷ and strategic understanding of how culture can be better used to humanise what politics demonises, it appears that it fails to capture the organisational dimension of culture or corporate culture which refers to “typical ways societies structure

power relations in institutions, organise groups to achieve goals, and promote economic activities” (Ferguson, 2001).¹⁸

The theory of social constructivism, in particular, brings us to a much closer understanding of the fabric of cultural formations and how these inform international orders. The body of constructivist literature has contributed to the debates of IR in many significant ways. The theory emerged in the 1980s with the writings of Nicholas Onuf whose constructivist assumptions take a more critical perspective on how we come to gather knowledge about the world,¹⁹ Martha Finnemore’s study of the life cycle of norms and their implications on human rights,²⁰ and Alexander Wendt’s mainstream constructivism,²¹ the assumptions of which are of interest to the present study.

The social theory of constructivism suggests that the way states and institutions interact has no reality outside the intersubjective understandings of one another, suggesting “difference across context rather than a single objective reality”.²² This opens the door to exploring and understanding the dramatic—and, sometimes, uncalculated—changes in the international system, and raises questions about transition—and, sometimes, meteoric shift—from conflict to cooperation, or the opposite for that matter. Constructivists focus their analysis on the social dimensions of international relations and argue that these relations are constituted, not fundamentally through the distribution of material forces, but through shared ideas and collective knowledge—hence the distribution of knowledge instead of the distribution of material capabilities. Suggestive as it is, mutual constitution is a central assumption of constructivism.²³ The argument here is that the international system as a social structure “leaves more space for agency, that is for the individual or state to influence their environment, as well as to be influenced by it”.²⁴ The ideational standpoint from which constructivists depart suggests that international relations are not given *a priori* in the same way we speak of rocks, trees, and the solar system. Constructivists use the term “social

facts” or “social realities” to argue that in an anarchic international system, relations between states are constituted on the basis of “intersubjective agreement” (or collective knowledge) among the actors, be they states or individuals.²⁵ That is, they exist in virtue of some procedural, common beliefs about one another. This is well captured by Wendt’s ground-breaking article, now an inscription of constructivism, “Anarchy Is What the States Make of It”.²⁶

Identity-Alterity formation is apparently one of the staple issues in constructivist critique. The significant “breakthrough” of constructivists is their endorsement of the social sciences in an attempt to arrive at a middle ground theory, or *via media*, that mediates between the grand principles and the complexity of the social world. Indeed, the constructivist debate with realism and neoliberalism takes place,²⁷ first and foremost, at a meta-theoretical level. In other words, positions taken on the philosophy of social science that inform “the way people theorize and, indeed, ‘see’ the world”.²⁸

The intellectual and theoretical development of constructivism originates partly in Immanuel Kant’s philosophical accounts on subjective knowledge and the sociological accounts of Max Weber’s call for an interpretive understanding of actors’ actions as well as those of Anthony Giddens on the agent-structure problematic. Wendt draws on Kant’s ideas on obtaining knowledge about the world, which posit that our knowledge of the world is always subjective as long as its perception is filtered through human consciousness.²⁹ Pure objective knowledge about the world (or what Kant terms “*ding an sich*” in reference to the ‘thing-in-itself’) can only be reached through an “intersubjective understanding” among individuals.

In sociology, Weber’s informative propositions on understanding human interaction is significant in the constructivist analysis. In order to explore and understand human interaction, Weber suggests, we need ‘*verstehen*’, that is, a new interpretive understanding. Wendt uses Weber’s ideas to argue that since

international relations are basically interactions among individual actors, understanding their relations means to explore the meanings assigned to these relations which are socially constructed. International relations is not a physical phenomenon that we can merely describe in the same way we describe the physical world; it is rather an intellectual and social phenomenon to which specific meanings are assigned.³⁰

Equally significant are the sociological accounts of Anthony Giddens' theory of structuration (1984).³¹ His theory discusses the agent-structure problem (what influences what in a social structure). The structurationist proposition gives equal weight to both structure and its agents. Primary effects are reduced to none of the two elements because "[s]tructures do constrain actors, but actors can also transform structures by thinking about them and acting on them in new ways".³² Wendt uses the premises of the structuration theory in a twofold way. First, he emphasises constitutive rather than causal relations in a social structure. Structure has neither a top-down effect nor a bottom-up one. Second, by incorporating the insights of the structurationist proposition, constructivists suggest that the relationships between structure and agents are less rigid and more dynamic,³³ hence the possibility of change.

While the dynamism of the international structure is suggestive of congruity and unity as well as the inherent heterogeneity of cultural formations across the polity, the constructivist account reduces culture to a set of disaggregate norms that can be communicated and substantiated through common knowledge and "collective mentalities", which are necessary to establish cooperation and coexistence. Yet we learn from anthropologists and sociologists that "any claims to underlying cultural unity on the scale of international orders must necessarily obscure the differences, contradictions, and contestations that characterize any cultural landscape, while at the same time neglecting the institutional construction of aspects of unity".³⁴ Moreover, while constructivists assume agency and

difference across the context, it does not tell us exactly how the inherent heterogeneity of cultural formations affect the development of international orders. Culture, Reus-Smit notes, “is not just a mess of meanings, symbols, and practices—a grab bag of atomized resources for strategic use—it is patterned and structured: even its contradictions bind as much they divide.”³⁵

4. Alterity Formation Regimes

Another way to look at the effects of these diversity regimes is post-colonialism. This article is particularly interested in the extent to which these diversity regimes are integral to the ways in which postcolonial orders prioritise and organise cultural differences in alignment with the established distribution of political authority. Indeed, decolonising histories and narratives, in particular, bare the very moment where these diversity regimes are iteratively mobilised to address grievances about existing or past forms of recognition.³⁶

Postcolonial theory allows for a critical take on the Eurocentric character of contemporary international order. The mainstream narrative puts forward that the foundations of the modern international order started with the Westphalian settlement, to then spread to other continents. The Industrial Revolution empowered Westerners with technological and economic superiority compared to non-Westerners, and so made it plausible to propagandise the capitalist system elsewhere.³⁷ Ultimately, the narrative goes on, this brought modernity and progress to foreign peoples.³⁸ This grand narrative which manifests European paternalism is not without problems. This narrative also comes embedded with hierarchical formations of alterity and otherness that have characterised the order of the international system.³⁹ Meanwhile, countries with colonial legacies and vulnerable national economies are forced to carry out the burden of recovery, but also adapt to the new world order. Such adaptation leaves a lot more confusion on the side of culture. Within all these intense shifts, postcolonial orders exist somewhere between the burden of cultural recovery in an increasingly intensified

internationalisation of cultures worldwide and an accelerated but dependent economic growth that is often challenged by structural stumbling blocks and the dominance of a global market.⁴⁰

Although much of the early postcolonial critique was concerned with resistance, the emphasis on recognition and recovery is a particular range that could be seen across the postcolonial body of writing (Edward Said, Gayatri Spivak, and Homi Bhabha). While part of this body of writing takes a remarkably redemptive stand with regard to the experience of colonialism and the effects of orientalism (Said), the works of Bhabha and Spivak, in particular, understand the colonial encounter as an “ambivalent” experience for both the postcolonial subject and the coloniser: “the place of difference and otherness or the space of the adversarial ... is never entirely on the outside or implacably oppositional.”⁴¹ Given the “hybrid” and “syncretic” nature of postcolonial orders, the substrata of otherness and difference are imbued with an inherently “inevitable ambivalence”. In such colonial contexts, subjects are involved in a process of hybridisation and mimicry. For Spivak, the inherent heterogeneity of narratives as well as a peculiar focus on the periphery and the marginal should be the foci of interest. She notes: “I am critical of the binary opposition coloniser/colonised. I try to examine the heterogeneity of ‘colonial power’ and to disclose the complicity of the two poles of that opposition as it constitutes the disciplinary enclave of the critique of imperialism.”⁴²

Reinterpreting colonial histories is relevant to the understanding of the effects of contemporary cultural and identarian formations on the development of international order. The ways in which these formations occur are the exact manifestations of cultural diversity regimes discussed previously, which re-define order and power relations between the ex-colonial subjects and the former colonisers—aspects of which can be directly found in the “reconciliation” and “rapprochement” policies, but also in modern practices of public diplomacy,

international law and institutions. Nevertheless, the ambivalence of the colonial encounter does also manifest itself through new claims for recognition against past atrocities, genocides (ethnic cleansing) or even misconceptions about entire societies. Such new reinterpretations of the colonial and postcolonial experience draws along less essentialist understandings of culture and power; these are entangled in rather culturally syncretic and heterogeneous contexts. Power can materialise through material capabilities but also through political authority. Master narratives of European paternalism, universalism, and cultural homogeneity are, then, challenged by the discourses of the peripheral and the subaltern. These discourses declare rather an interest in the constructions of Self and Other.

Modern diplomacies are a vital channel for such constructions. Cultural diplomacy and soft power, in particular, accommodate these constructions in the form of discursive formations and representations. Cultural diplomacy is a by-product of the bi-polarity that characterised world order during the Cold War, a period of resurgent liberation movements and independence, as well. It was only until the second half of the twentieth-century that cultural diplomacy had gained currency as an official state activity. An essential component of public diplomacy, cultural diplomacy carries a “quest for tourist dollar as well as the battle for the hearts and minds”.⁴³ It is best defined as “the exchange of ideas, information, art, and other aspects of culture among nations and their peoples in order to foster mutual understanding”.⁴⁴ The directionality of cultural diplomacy practices, then, suggest a rather pluralist context of exchange and mutual understanding. But along these lines also fall the expectation of where and how exactly this exchange takes place. Indeed, what Smit-Reus calls diversity regimes also fall into the category of these diplomatic representations of Self and Other. The constructivist interpretation of the international structure provides us with a practical taxonomy,

or “cultures of anarchy”,⁴⁵ that captures the formation of alterity and otherness in the making of world order: Hobbesian, Lockean and Kantian cultures.

Interestingly enough, a key premise in the constructivist interpretation of anarchy and order is the distinction between private knowledge and shared knowledge. The former refers to the set of beliefs someone holds and others do not. States’ private knowledge, then, is reduced to domestic ideological considerations and these can affect their external behaviour towards other states. Shared knowledge, or “culture”, refers to socially and intersubjectively shared ideas and beliefs which are embedded in many cultural forms such as norms, international laws, international institutions and organisations. In the constructivist critique of order and power, culture takes a specific meaning: “culture is not a sector or sphere of society distinct from economy or polity, but present wherever shared knowledge is found. If economy and polity are institutionally distinct spheres in a society, as in capitalism, therefore, that is because culture constitutes them as such”.⁴⁶

Other scholars who addressed the issue of alterity formation in reference to diplomacy include Costas Constantinou (2004),⁴⁷ Paul Sharp (1999),⁴⁸ James Der Derian and Michael Shapiro (1989),⁴⁹ Raymond Cohen (1991),⁵⁰ and Edward Said (1978 and 1993).⁵¹ Of interest to the present study, Said’s orientalism stands out as a peculiar framework that captures the deeper effects of culture and cultural representations on the development of postcolonial order.

The discursive formations and representations of alterity and otherness, which I argue are another manifestation of Smit-Reus’ diversity regimes, rest upon a particular view of order. That is, order is based on a characteristic distinctiveness that drives interaction among actors (or states), and which, in turn, constitutes different alterities: “ally,” “rival,” “friend,” and “exotic.” These alterities should be seen, respectively, as corresponding to Wendt’s three cultures of anarchy (Hobbesian, Lockean, and Kantian) and Said’s orientalism.

4.1. The Other as enemy/Barbarian: Hobbesian Culture

In a Hobbesian culture of anarchy, states construct a dichotomous process of interaction and view other states as enemies or rivals. Wendt draws upon Thomas Hobbes' idea of "*bellum omnium contra omnes*" (war of all against all). Hobbesian anarchy induces enmity as a position of the Other along with its implications on the Self. Therefore, states seek survival as their ultimate priority. "Enemies", Wendt asserts, "are constituted by representations of the Other as an actor who (1) does not recognize the right of the Self to exist as an autonomous being, and therefore (2) will not willingly limit its violence toward the Self."⁵² The act of not being fully recognised as a free and legitimate entity by the Other implies a "deep revisionism",⁵³ which involves the Other's attempt to "revise" the entity's life and liberty as two properties of a given state. Linked to this is the proposition that in a Hobbesian culture of anarchy, distribution of knowledge might be missing since states interact on a private basis and call each other for constant revisionism that may lead to conflict and war. The implication of the Hobbesian anarchy, for analytical purposes, seems to reflect the hardcore of realism: balance of power and distributions of material might. By extension, the realist discourse about world politics seems to focus only on one logic of anarchy, namely the Hobbesian one.⁵⁴

Three degrees of internalisation are involved in the Hobbesian anarchy. First is *force*; states are forced to comply with the cultural norms of enmity generated by the private/collective knowledge by means of threatening or coercing. Second is *prize*. At this degree of internalisation, states comply with the cultural norms induced by enmity not because they are forced to, but because they decide that compliance serves their self-interest. Third is *legitimacy*; states comply with the cultural norms generated by the Hobbesian culture because they think the norms are legitimate.

4.2. The Other as ally/rival: Lockean Culture

In a Lockean culture, states view each other as rivals. That is, they recognise each other's right to liberty, life, and sovereignty. The "war of all against all" is substituted for "live and let live". Recognising each other's sovereignty has implications on the posture of the Self; states do not necessarily tend to eliminate each other, but violence is not precluded either. Wendt argues that "rivals are constituted by representations about Self and Other with respect to violence, but these representations are less threatening. ... [R]ivals expect each other to act as if they recognize their sovereignty."⁵⁵ Rivalry, therefore, is constituted as an intersubjective belief that orients states' interactions with one another.

Three degrees of cultural internalisation of the Lockean anarchy are discussed in this regard. As with the Hobbesian anarchy, Lockean anarchy starts with a weak degree of commitment to shared ideas and norms about sovereignty. States are coerced to comply with the norms of sovereignty. A second degree of commitment implies the idea that states' compliance with the sovereignty norms generate more exogenous interests such as territorial security and trade. A third and strong degree of commitment to the norms of sovereignty is reached when states view them as legitimate. They act in ways which make it possible for them to instrumentalise these norms and define their national and transnational interests with the interests of international law.

4.3. The Other as friend: Kantian Culture

In a Kantian anarchic culture, states exhibit friendship roles in conducting their relations. Thus, states have no intention to violate each other. Rather, "non-violence" and "team play" emerge as the cultural norms of Kantian anarchy. Wendt draws on Emmanuel Kant's ideas of Perpetual Peace to argue that states settle their disputes without conflict or war. He notes that substantial literature of IR discusses more enduring conflicts and rivalries but less attention was ever addressed to "enduring friendships"; he goes as far as to suggest that the concept

of “friend”, unlike “enemies”, is “unauthorised in social theory, especially in IR”.⁵⁶

The Kantian culture is so hard a case for materialists to come to grips with. The relatively weak degree of commitment to shared ideas within the Hobbesian and Lockean anarchies make it possible for the materialist ontology assumptions explain the use of coercion and violence in making states comply with the norms of the status quo; but problematic to this case is the Kantian anarchy. What makes it too “hard” to explain is that the shift from the first degree to the second degree of cultural internalisation – in which case friendship is deployed as a strategy to gain sympathy for one’s own interests – does not involve coercion. This is largely because in Kantian anarchy, states have no desire to violate each other. Wendt asserts that “[c]ollective security poses a more serious challenge for a coercion theory. Here coercion has to explain not only non-violence but cooperation, and, moreover, do so in a way that distinguishes it from alliance behavior.”⁵⁷

By virtue of its nature, the friendship structure of Kantian anarchy allows the deep internalisation of the shared ideas of “perpetual peace”. Thus, in a third strong degree of commitment to the shared Kantian norms, the implications of friendship on states dictate that the security of the Other is conceived of as the security of the Self, creating what is known as a “pluralistic security community”; states “live in peace but go their separate ways.”⁵⁸ The Westphalian Peace Treaty of 1648 which brought to an end the Eighty Years’ War is taken as an example to illustrate the point where the shared norms of a cooperative culture between European states took over the Hobbesian logic of “war of all against all”. Centuries later, the end of the Cold War marked yet another demarcation line that led to a structural change in the international system and gave European states their identity of cooperation and friendship by forming the European Community and later (since 1995) the European Union.

These three cultures of anarchy, with different degrees of internalisation, provide states with a social structure constituted mainly by the ideas and norms advanced by each anarchic culture. In this respect, states' identities, interests, and hence power are constituted by the ideas implied by which anarchic culture dominates the status quo. Change is dependent on the beliefs and ideas believed to be true, and any change with regard to these beliefs result in a change of the social structure and relations between states. State actors *decide* to be enemies, rivals, or friends.

4.4. The Other as Exotic: the Orientalist Effect

It is worth noting that Wendt's conceptualisation of these three cultures becomes problematic when discussing the case of postcolonial societies. First, these three cultures concern the historical formation of international relations in Western societies. Second, postcolonial societies present a theoretical limitation to Wendt's classification because *how* these societies relate to each other and to Western societies cannot be merely captured in terms of enmity, rivalry, or friendship. This is largely because the shared knowledge with former colonial powers is determined by a colonial heritage that informs the perception of postcolonial order.

Edward Said's works, *Orientalism: Western Conceptions of the Orient* (1978) and *Culture and Imperialism* (1993) emphasise that Orientalism is an underpinning foundation of the imperialist movement of Western societies, and has three applications: (i) Orientalism as an area of studies dominated more precisely by the nineteenth century specialists and teachers in Oriental languages and culture, and which is based on the ontological and epistemological distinction between the Occident and the Orient; (ii) Orientalism as a discourse and a corporate institution whose "Western style" dominates and takes over the Orient, sustaining the dialects of centre/periphery and superiority/inferiority, and (iii) Orientalism as a set of representations, images and words – myths and lies – that

confine the Orient and Orientals between the fantasies of exoticism and cultural denigration. The production of the “exotic” in culture is a dialectic process in which the Other is framed in an aesthetically rendered entity, or as Graham Huggan notes: “the exotic is not, as is often supposed, an inherent *quality* to be found ‘in’ certain people, distinctive objects, or specific places; exoticism describes, rather, a particular mode of aesthetic *perception*—one which renders people, objects and places strange even as it domesticates them, and which effectively manufactures otherness even as it claims to surrender to its immanent mystery.”⁵⁹

Following Said’s analysis, colonialism falls into two main stages: first as a coercive and violent conquest, and later as an ideological appropriation through culture. Equally important, colonialism is not simply an encounter of imperialism that ended once and for all at some historical trajectories. What is characterised as colonialism goes beyond the end of the colonial period to include a set of practices—and, indeed, a set of diversity regimes—that re-dictate forms of power relations between newly independent states and former colonial powers. Order has to determine who can speak, and that is why this alternate space of postcolonial theory that focuses on marginality and identity⁶⁰ construction is relevant to the discussion of culture and order in the modern world.

5. Conclusion

The governance and organisation of cultural diversity is a fundamental premise of maintaining and reinforcing political legitimacy in world politics. Although the neoliberal perspective defines the contemporary international order as a multicultural, homogeneous, and inclusive polity, it is also an order whereby culture is politically configured to maintain authoritative legitimacy. Diversity, in fact, as Reus-Smit and Philips show in their account for culture and order, has historically challenged order-builders.⁶¹ Such legitimising challenges requires the

mobilisation of cultural diversity regimes: “systems of norms and practices that simultaneously configure authority and construct diversity.”⁶²

Disciplinary debates in mainstream IR draw along essentialist views of culture—an epiphenomenal event, only loosely constitutive of the international order, and only relates to world politics in ways that are (preferably) empirically causal. This essentialist view of culture suggests that a culturally homogeneous context is a prerequisite condition to maintain order. Meanwhile, open, rules-based institutions such as foreign policy establishment, diplomacy, and international law are argued to be capable of accommodating diversity under the “unity-triumphs-over-diversity” thesis. According to this conception, thus, institutions have but only a “neutralising effect” through which culture is strategically instrumentalised in order to create opportunities for cooperation and coordination.

The constructivist critique (Wendt’s taxonomy of cultures binding the international scene) and postcolonial theory (presented here by Said’s writings) bring us much closer to the understanding of these diversity regimes. The discursive formations and representations of alterity and otherness, which I argue are another manifestation of diversity regimes, rest upon a particular view of contemporary world order: the characteristic distinctiveness that drives interaction among actors, and which, in turn, constitutes different alterities: “ally,” “rival,” “friend,” and “exotic.”

Endnotes

[1] In recent years, there has been an increasing amount of literature on the implications of new conjunctions of power and cultural difference for the future of the modern international order. See Ikenberry 2011; Philips 2011; Goh 2013; Kissinger 2014; and Reus-Smit 2018.

[2] The term IR is the shorthand name for the academic subject and scholarship of international relations. The term "international relations" with lower cases refers generally to the phenomenon of relationships and interactions between states.

[3] See Hurrell 2020.

- [4] See Philips and Reus-Smit 2020, especially chapter 2.
- [5] See Reus-Smit 2017, Reus-Smit 2018; and Philips and Reus-Smit 2020.
- [6] Reus-Smit 2017, 26.
- [7] Ibid.
- [8] Ibid., 26.
- [9] See Philips and Reus-Smit 2020, especially chapters 1 and 2.
- [10] Williams 1976, 76.
- [11] See Huntington 1996.
- [12] See Ketzenstein 1996.
- [13] See Wendt 1999.
- [14] See Nye 2004.
- [15] See Ninkovich 1981; Cummings 2003; Arndt 2005; Schneider 2010; and Jurková 2015.
- [16] For more views on the philosophy of social science in IR, see Kurki and Wight 2013.
- [17] Classical realism, social constructivism and neoliberalism (represented by English School scholars) are three competing traditions in mainstream IR that have invoked the question of culture and international politics in one way or another, but nowhere is the nature of culture itself probed. These traditions of thinking take particular theoretical assumptions about culture and international order-building because each theory asks different questions about ontology, methodology, and epistemology. They direct in a fundamental way the way we theorise the international system. Realism and neoliberalism draw upon a materialist and positivist ontology. The materialist stance accounts for the distribution of material capabilities, and these are measured by means of military and economic assets. According to mainstream IR theory, the structure of the international system is formed “solely by differences in polarity (number of major powers), and structural change is measured solely by transitions from one polarity distribution to another”; see Wendt 1999, 16.
- [18] Ferguson 2001.
- [19] See Onuf 1989.
- [20] See Finnemore 1996.
- [21] See Wendt 1999 and Hopf 1998.
- [22] Fierke 2013, 189.

- [23] Constructivists emphasise constitutive relations rather than causal relations within structure. The agent-structure problematic takes a huge chapter in the constructivist analysis. Building mainly on Anthony Giddens' concept of structuration, constructivists assume that the relationship between agents and structure is reducible to none of these elements – structure has neither a top-down effect nor a bottom-up effect. Both the agents and the structure are reducible to the process of structuration. Agents shape structure, and structure shape agents in return.
- [24] Fierke 2013, 191.
- [25] See Kubalkova 2001.
- [26] See Wendt 1992.
- [27] These disagreements initiated a whole debate known in IR scholarship as the Third Debate. See Kurki and Wight 2013.
- [28] See Kurki and Wight 2013, 15.
- [29] See Jackson and Sørensen 2013.
- [30] Ibid.
- [31] See Giddens 1984.
- [32] Jackson and Sørensen 2013, 210.
- [33] Ibid., 213.
- [34] Reus-Smit 2017, 15.
- [35] Ibid., 6.
- [36] In international relations, some states deny the legal status of others, stigmatising their practices or even their culture. Such occurrences are common in modern diplomacy. French political scientist Bertrand Badie draws on a social psychology approach to explain the effects of such acts of humiliation on international relations. According to Badie, these actions appear to be the outcome of a colonial past, a failed decolonisation, a mistaken vision of globalisation and a very dangerous post-bipolar reconstruction. See Badie 2014.
- [37] See Bull and Watson 1984.
- [38] For a more detailed discussion on the postcolonial critique of IR theory, see Seth 2011.
- [39] For a more detailed discussion of the Eurocentric character of IR theory, see Hobson 2012.
- [40] See Acharya 2018.
- [41] Bhabha 1985, 152.
- [42] Spivak 1989, 5.

[43] See Bound, Briggs, Holden and Jones 2007.

[44] See Cummings 2003.

[45] See Wendt 1992.

[46] Wendt 1999, 142.

[47] See Constantinou 2004.

[48] See Sharp 1999.

[49] See Derian and Shapiro 1989.

[50] See Cohen 1991.

[51] See Said 1978 and 1993.

[52] Wendt 1999, 260.

[53] Ibid., 261.

[54] Ibid.

[55] Ibid., 279.

[56] Ibid., 298.

[57] Ibid., 303.

[58] Ibid., 299.

[59] Huggan 2001, 13.

[60] For strong points of view on different aspects of identity formation and culture, see Hall 1992, 1993 and 1996.

[61] See Philips and Reus-Smit 2020.

[62] Reus-Smit 2017, 26.

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